

ASD7 (biotype 3) were prepared for morphological examination as follows: 1) boil in 95% ethanol for about 10 min; 2) macerate in lukewarm 10% NaOH for 10-15 min; 3) wash in 95% ethanol and boil for 15-20 min in chloral-phenol (1:1 part chloral hydrate and phenol crystals); 4) clear in creosote for 10 min; and 5) mount body parts on glass micro-slides using Hoyer's medium (30 g gum arabic, 50 ml water, 200 g chloral hydrate, 20 ml glycerine). Antennae in glycerol medium were also mounted on slides so they could be moved freely during microscopic examination.

Camera lucida drawings of selected structures were made at 20X objective of a phase contrast microscope. More than 100 morphological characters of the rostrum, including mandibular stylets, legs, and antennae, were measured and evaluated. Characters were examined

separately in both sexes and their morphs, i.e., macropterous male, macropterous female, brachypterous male, and brachypterous female.

Multiple discriminant analysis using stepwise selection through Wilk's specification indicated distinct segregation of the three biotypes. The characters of the rostrum, legs, and antennae common to both sexes and their respective morphs contributed to the separation of biotypes. Scatter diagrams, based on computed discriminant scores of the three biotypes, showed a high degree of segregation (see figure). Hoppers classified using leg and antennal characters exhibited a 100% probability of correct morphological identification of the three biotypes.

We are using these criteria to evaluate allopatric populations of BPH biotypes from other geographical areas.

Discriminant scores of three biotypes of *N. lugens* based on rostral, leg, and antennal characters of brachypterous females. The numbers indicate biotype designation; the asterisk (*) indicates a group centroid. IRR1, 1980.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Yield response of 10 rices to different nitrogen levels

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TKM9 cultivation is increasing in Tamil Nadu, particularly in the south. During 1981 sornavari (Jun-Jul to Sep-Oct) TKM9, ADT36, CO 41, IET4786, and two prerelease lines, TM3320 and TM3324, were compared for yield performance at different nitrogen application levels.

IR50, IET4786, TM8089, and TM8090 were tested during 1982 navarai (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr).

Soil at the experimental site had pH 7.6, 0.64% organic carbon, 55 kg available phosphorus/ha, and 368 kg available potassium/ha. Nitrogen was applied at 0, 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg/ha in a strip-plot design with 2 replications.

During sornavari TKM9 yielded higher than other varieties at all nitrogen application levels (Table 1). IR50 yielded highest during navarai (Table 2). Both varieties yielded best at 120 kg N/ha. □

Table 1. Yield performance of rices grown at 5 nitrogen levels, sornavari 1981, Tirur, India.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)						Mean
	TKM9	IET4786	ADT36	CO 41	TM3320	TM3324	
0	4.5	3.3	3.4	3.7	3.1	3.0	3.5
40	5.6	3.5	4.3	4.1	3.5	3.4	4.1
80	6.4	5.2	5.3	4.6	4.5	4.2	5.0
120	7.2	5.3	5.6	5.2	5.0	4.7	5.5
160	6.6	5.9	6.3	5.9	5.5	4.8	5.8
Mean	6.0	4.6	5.0	4.7	4.0	4.0	

CD

Varieties

0.2**

N levels

0.4**

Interaction

ns

**Significant at 1% level. NS = not significant.

Table 2. Yields of varieties grown at 5 nitrogen levels, navarai 1982, Tirur, India.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean
	IET4786	IR50	TM8089	TM8090	
0	1.9	3.4	3.1	3.7	3.0
40	3.2	4.9	4.8	4.8	4.4
80	4.1	6.1	5.4	5.7	5.3
120	4.6	7.4	7.0	7.3	6.6
160	4.4	7.3	6.1	6.0	6.0
Mean	3.6	5.8	5.3	5.5	

CD

Varieties

0.2**

N levels

0.4**

Interaction

Sub at main

0.3**

Main at sub

0.3**

**Significant at 1% level.